

ISic0024

I.Sicily inscription 0024

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [I]mp(eratori) Caes(ari) G(aio) Valerio
2. [D]i,ocletiano Pio Fel(ici)
3. [in]v(icto) Aug(usto) pontif(ici) max(imo)
4. [tr]ib(unicia) pot(estate) co(n)s(uli) II p(atri) p(atriciae) proco(n)s(uli)
5. res p(ublica) Panhorm(itanorum) d(evota) n(umini) m(aiestati)q(ue) eius d(ecurionum) d(ecreto)

Apparatus

Text of

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491784

EDR 137833

EDCS 22000868

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7282 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650790>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 24

Raepsaet-Charlier, M.-Th. 1974. A propos du récent catalogue d'inscriptions latines du musée de Palerme. *Latomus*. 33: 124-127. At 126

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